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The Rate of Non-Participation in Work in the Italian Regions During the Period 2018-2022

It decreased by an average of 17.34% between 2018 and 2022

Istat calculates the value of the labor non-participation rate. The rate of non-participation in work is the ratio between the sum of "available" unemployed and inactive people (people who have not looked for work in the last 4 weeks but are available to work), and the sum of the labor force (set of employed and unemployed) and inactive "available", referring to the population between 15 and 74 years. The data is available between 2018 and 2022 in the Italian regions and macro-regions.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the rate of non-participation in work in 2022. Sicily is in first place in terms of value of the rate of non-participation in work in 2022 with a value of 35.3, followed by Campania with a value of 33.3 and from Calabria with a value of 33 units. In the middle of the table are Lazio with a value of 14.5 units, followed by Umbria with a value of 12.2 units and Liguria with a value of 11.2 units. Lombardy closes the ranking with a value of 8.5 units, followed by Veneto with a value of 7.8 units and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 5.9 units. Lombardy closes the ranking with a value of 8.5 units, followed by Veneto with a value of 7.8 units and Trentino Alto Adige with a value of 5.9 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the rate of non-participation in work between 2018 and 2022. Trentino Alto Adige is in first place in terms of value of the percentage change in the rate of non-participation in work between 2018 and 2022 with a value equal to -9.23% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.50 units up to a value of 5.90 units. Campania follows with a variation from an amount of 37.50 units up to a value of 33.30 units or equal to a variation of -11.20%. Emilia Romagna is in third place with a variation from an amount of 10.00 units up to 8.80 units or equal to -12.00%. In the middle of the table we find Sardinia with a variation from 27.90 units up to 23.10 units or equal to a variation of -17.20%. Umbria follows with a variation from an amount of 14.80 units up to a value of 12.20 units equivalent to a value of -17.57% and Puglia with a value from 30.90 units up to a value of 25.40 units or equal to a variation of -17.80%. The Marche closes the ranking with a variation from an amount of 13.80 units up to 10.30 units or equal to a variation of -25.36%, followed by Liguria with a value equal to -26.80% corresponding to a reduction from 15.30 units up to 11.20 units and from Veneto with a value equal to -27.10% equal to a variation from 10.70 units up to 7.80 units. On average between 2018 and 2022 the value of the rate of non-participation in the labor market decreased by -17.34%.

The rate of non-participation in work in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. The value of the rate of non-participation in work in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022 went from an amount of 37.2 units to a value of 32.1 units or equal to an amount of -5.10 units corresponding to -13.71%. The value of the non-participation rate in the South went from an amount

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of 34.7 units to a value of 29.8 units or equal to a variation of -4.90 units corresponding to -14.12%. The non-participation rate in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 33.5 units to a value of 28.7 units or equal to a variation of -4.80 units equal to -14.33%. The non-participation rate in Central Italy decreased from a value of 15.7 units to a value of 12.4 units or equal to -21.02%. The rate of non-participation in work in the North-West decreased from 11.6 units to 9.3 units or equal to a reduction of -2.30 units equal to -19.83%. The non-participation rate in Northern Italy decreased from an amount of 11 units to a value of 8.8 units or equal to an amount of -2.20 units equal to -20.00%. The non-participation rate in the North-East went from an amount of 10.1 units up to 8.1 units or equal to an amount of -2.00 units equal to -19.80%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of three clusters:

- *Cluster 1:* Friuli Venezia Giulia, Valle d'Aosta, Lombardy, Piedmont, Tuscany, Veneto, Emilia Romagna, Marche, Umbria, Trentino Alto Adige, Liguria, Lazio, Abruzzo;
- *Cluster 2:* Calabria, Campania, Sicily;
- *Cluster 3:* Sardinia, Basilicata, Molise, Puglia.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters we note the following orientation: C2>C3>C1. That is, the southern regions lead the Italian regions in terms of the rate of non-participation in work. However, even within the southern regions there are significant differences with Calabria, Campania and Sicily which have higher values than Sardinia, Basilicata, Molise and Puglia. Abruzzo is the only region in Southern Italy that is part of cluster 1, i.e. the most virtuous cluster in terms of lack of participation in work. The result is therefore a clear contrast between the southern regions and the central-northern regions.

Conclusions. The value of the non-participation rate in the Italian regions has significantly decreased in all Italian regions and macro-regions. On average, considering the regions, the rate of non-participation in work decreased by 17.34%. However, it is necessary to consider that there are significant differences between Northern, Central and Southern Italy. In fact, the rate of non-participation in work decreased rapidly in Central Italy between 2018 and 2022 with a value of -21.02%, and also in the North with -20.00%, while in the South it decreased by only 14.12%. Furthermore, considered in absolute value, the value of the non-participation rate in the South recorded in 2022 is equal to 240% of the same value recorded in the Center and equal to 338% of the value in Northern Italy. Local, regional, interregional and macro-regional labor markets are characterized by significant inequalities and inefficiencies which prevent, especially the southern population, from being able to access broader participation in the labor market and with greater possibilities of connecting work to income and the overall improvement of individual and collective life.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

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